

ADVANTAGES OF INFORMATION COMMUNICATION TECHNOLOGIES

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ABSTRACT

In the article is considered some aspects of distance learning technology introduction into higher educational institutions.

In the current conditions, when the need for highly qualified pedagogical personnel is increasing, it is necessary to train teachers as personnel capable of mastering modern pedagogical and information technologies. The implementation of these tasks consists in improving the existing system of training employees of public education, developing it in accordance with the requirements of electronic education, entrenching basic knowledge related to the specialty in public educational institutions, establishing various forms of training, "During the An orientation towards education based on the principle of "reading" is required throughout life. In this sense, improving professional qualifications and retraining of public education employees occupies a special place in the system of continuous education of our republic. The main objective is envisaged This is continuous improvement and improvement of the general attitude and professional skills of the teaching staff. Today, interactive methods, innovative pedagogy and information technologies are used by many teachers directly in the teaching process. In this way, the teacher uses less energy during the lesson and achieves efficiency by conveying more information, and the students retain the information for a long time by seeing it with their eyes.

In education, these technologies that teach students to search for their own knowledge, study and analyze it independently, recognize their mistakes and draw their own conclusions are the joint activities of the student and the teacher. happens through showing. If information technologies are used in the implementation of this activity: in particular, a computer, a projector, an overhead projector, a TV, DVDs, then something that a good teacher always lacks is missing, namely saving time and the ability to retain knowledge increases. In our opinion, we

will present the approach to using information and communication technologies in teaching. When a new topic statement is made in the form of an electronic textbook or an electronic film, a presentation tool, the possibility of memorizing information increases. Because the ability of the visual organs to transmit information is higher than that of the hearing organs. This, in turn, allows the visual system to provide approximately 90% of the information received by the student, thereby accelerating cognitive activity. The first 20 minutes of learning are the most effective, after 30 minutes the motivation to continue learning begins to decrease rapidly. These suggestions are designed to keep the student's attention for a longer period of time and to keep them well remembered.

The more sensory channels are used during perception, the higher the quantity and quality of the knowledge remembered. If the knowledge is only imparted through lectures (through passive listening), after 3 days you can only remember 25% of it. If it is given through lectures (listening), showing and demonstrating (seeing, holding, etc.) and discussing, then 75% can be accessed after 3 days. If several sensory channels are used together when perceiving knowledge, the process of transferring information from short memory to long memory is accelerated, which is the basis of cognition. The degree of influence of teaching methods on the achievement level of students: 1. Lecture – 5% of what we hear. 2. Reading – 10% of what we read. 3. Video method, demonstration – 20% of what we see. 4. Demonstration of experience – 30% of what we see and hear. 5. Debate – 40% of our discussions. 6. Exercises – 50% of what we read, write, speak. 7. Simulation game, work in small groups, design - 75% of what we independently studied, analyzed and discussed, defended and demonstrated. 8. Reference text, problem situation, teaching others - 90% of what we have independently learned, analyzed and discussed and what we have taught others. is stored in memory. The 21st century, the age of information technologies, shows every year that this century is not called that for nothing. Such changes have an impact on the organization and implementation of educational processes.

One of such changes is the rapid introduction of multimedia lessons into the educational system. What is multimedia itself:

Multimedia is a multi-channel way of presenting information (text, image, animation, audio, video). That is, the quality of the information given during the lesson is presented to the student on the basis of technical means. Multimedia can be explained as follows.

Multimedia records are a collection of publications, demonstrations, visual, animated and sound records placed on CDs or other computer data carriers, as well as on devices that provide access to users at any time.

Multimedia environment is a technology that comprehensively (complexly) describes arbitrary types of media, providing joint processing of images (including animation-movement), speech, sound and documents.

Multimedia textbooks - textbooks on CD discs with high-order dynamics of visual materials using a multimedia environment.

Multimedia technology is a method of preparation of electronic documents, which includes the unified management of interactive software, visual and audio-effective, multi-programming of various situations.

The main condition for understanding and passing multimedia lessons is to be able to use technical tools, especially to know how to work with a computer. It is necessary for them to know how to work with the Power Point program, create slides, and animate them. When creating multimedia slides, it is necessary to pay attention to the following: the idea given on the slide should not exceed six lines. Often we try to display a whole page of text on the screen. However, many people do not read such slides. Metadata should be used as widely as possible.

Metadata - short information identifiers (indexes, keywords) designed to describe the meaning of information data (text, image, table, etc.).

- it is not recommended to use colors and animations that tire the eyes too much when placing information;

- taking into account motivation, it is recommended to use video, music, pictures related to the topic in the slides;

So, today we are proud of the fact that we live in the age of high technologies, but we must admit that information attacks are increasing due to the inappropriate use of these technologies by some evil forces. To protect our society from the flow of destructive and destructive information, especially to protect the inviolability of the spiritual world of our youth, our activity of forming a culture of using the Internet is carried out by state bodies, public organizations, self-government bodies of citizens, all institutions of civil society, calls parents, pedagogues and specialists for long-term continuous and systematic cooperation, of course.

The introduction of modern information and communication technologies into the educational process has led to the creation of a new form of education - distance education, in addition to traditional teaching methods.

In information and communication technologies education, listeners are spatially separated from each other and constantly communicate with each other with the help of specially created training courses, control forms, electronic communication and other technologies of the Internet. Distance education based on the use of Internet technology provides access to the global information and education network, performs new functions based on the principle of integration and interaction.

Information and communication technologies make it possible for all those who want to learn to continuously improve their skills. In the course of such training, the student learns independent educational and methodological materials in an interactive mode, passes control, performs control work under the direct guidance of the teacher and communicates with other members of the virtual learning group in the group. The use of ICT is mainly carried out in two ways. The first condition is technical equipment, and the second condition is the provision of special software:

1. Provision of technical equipment: computers, network devices, high-speed Internet networks, video conferencing equipment, etc.
2. Software includes a set of programs designed for this field.

Educational process management systems play a key role in the organization of distance education.

Teaching represents a structured and recursive process. All participants and objects involved in the same teaching scenarios should converge in the direction of intellectual activity through knowledge sharing, expert evaluation and consensus formation. In addition, they should be able to exchange information with each other through various types of mass media. Thus, it is important to build different teaching processes based on different teaching subjects and objects

The introduction of modern information and communication technologies into the educational process has led to the emergence of a new form of education - distance education, in addition to traditional teaching methods. Why is it necessary to create a theoretical basis for the introduction of information technologies in education, to create and implement distance education courses? Firstly, the teacher is becoming one of the sources of knowledge acquisition, not as an organizer of the educational process, and secondly, there is a sharp increase in information at the developing stage of scientific and technical development and the limitation of time to use it in the teaching process, as well as students the requirements of excellent training for professional activities require the introduction of modern technologies into the educational system. The fundamental changes taking place in the field of education in our country require the development of methodological support of the educational process in every educational institution. Wide implementation of modern information and communication technologies, in particular, introduction of distance education courses based on educational management systems:

- informatization of science fields;
- intellectualization of educational activities;
- deepening the processes of integration of participants in the educational system;
- leads to improvement of educational system infrastructure and its management mechanisms. Effective organization of pedagogical education processes based on modern information technologies:
- unification of pedagogues, computer programmers, relevant specialists into a team creating distance learning courses and electronic literature;

Widespread introduction of distance education in the system of professional development:

- acquisition of modern professional knowledge;
- in-depth mastering of the field of science through modeling of the studied phenomena and processes;
- expansion of the field of independent activity of the pedagogue due to the diverse organization of educational activities;
- individualization and differentiation of the teaching process based on the introduction of interactive communication opportunities;
- mastering the strategy of mastering educational materials by the pedagogue by using the capabilities of the artificial intelligence system;

- formation of information culture in him as a member of the information society;
 - presentation of the studied processes and phenomena by means of computer technologies is of great importance as it increases students' interest and activity in the basics of science.
- Therefore, one of the necessary conditions for improving the content of education is to increase the opportunities for students to acquire independent knowledge, to create the necessary conditions for the formation and development of electronic information resources of education.

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